

A New Pterocarpan Glycoside from *Trifolium pratense*

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TRIFOLIUM pratense (N.O. Leguminosae) is native from Kashmir to Garhwal, and is reported to be used as expectorant and also as an important ingredient for the treatment of ulcers. The present communication reports the isolation of maackianin 3-O-β-D-galactopyranoside from its roots.

The powdered, dried roots of *T. pratense* were extracted with methanol and the concentrated extract was worked up by column chromatography to get colourless needles, m.p. 153–55°, C₂₂H₂₂O₁₀, M⁺ 446; λ_{max} (EtOH) 273, 286 and 307 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 410, 1 720, 1 610, 1 585 and 1 500 cm⁻¹; δ 7.32, 6.63, 6.66, 6.35, 5.88, 5.43, 4.65, 3.72, 4.30, 4.42–4.5, 2.02, 2.05, 1.97 and 2.12.

On acid hydrolysis in dioxane–water², it yielded D-galactose (co-pc and tlc) and an aglycone which crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m.p. 180–82°, C₁₆H₁₂O₆, M⁺ 284; λ_{max} (MeOH) 218, 282 and 290 nm, λ_{max} (EtOH) 208, 236 and 285 nm, λ_{max} (EtOH+NaOH) 221, 255, 280 and 306 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 1 710, 1 620, 1 590, 1 385, 1 355, 1 290, 1 180, 1 150, 1 035, 850, 830 and 790 cm⁻¹; δ 7.32 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C₁-H), 6.63 (2H, m, C₇, C₈-H), 6.66 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, C₄-H), 6.35 (1H, s, C₁₀-H), 5.88 (2H, d, J 1 Hz, OCH₂O), 5.43 (1H, m, C_{11α}-H), 4.05 (1H, q, C_{6α}-H) and 3.72 (2H, m, C₆-H).

From physical and spectral data, the aglycone was identified as maackianin. Its identify was further confirmed by its conversion to acetyl derivative³, m.p. 179°, [α]_D²⁰ –176°.

Periodate oxidation⁴ and enzymatic hydrolysis⁵ indicated that the glycoside was made up of one mole of aglycone and one mol of sugar and having β-linkage. Absence of peak at λ_{max} (EtOH+NaOH) 255 in the uv spectra of the glycoside confirmed that the C₈-OH of pterocarpan was involved in glycosylation⁶. Permethylation⁷ of the glycoside showed that the C₁-OH of galactose was involved in glycoside linkage. Thus the glycoside was identified as maackianin 3-O-β-D-galactopyranoside.

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Chemical Investigation of *Echinops echinatus*

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THE medicinal uses¹⁻³ of the roots of *Echinops echinatus* (Fam. Compositae) prompted us to undertake the investigation on the roots of the plant wherefrom we have isolated ω-methylallophanic acid and allophanic acid.

The ethanolic extract of the air-dried powdered roots (5 kg) was methylated with diazomethane in ether. The methylated ethanol extract was separated on silica gel column using different solvents and their mixtures as eluents.

From the benzene eluate of the methylated ethanolic extract, a compound obtained was recrystallised from methanol as pinkish needles, m.p. 163°, C₄H₈N₂O₃; ν_{max} 3 415–3 310 (NH), 1 750–1 720 (N–COOCH₃), 1 690, 1 560–1 510 cm⁻¹ (HN–CO–NH); δ (100 MHz, CDCl₃), 2.81 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, HNCCH₃), 3.75 (3H, s, CO–OCH₃), 7.85 (1H, s, H₃C–NH) and 9.12 (1H, s, HN–CO)(D₂O exchangeable); m/z 132 (M⁺ 46%), 117(3.8%), 101(3.0%), 74(17.0%) and (24.0%). The compound was identified as ω-methylallophanic acid (as methyl ester, 1, lit.⁴ m.p. 163.5° as methyl ester).

The methanol eluate of the methylated ethanolic extract yielded a compound which was recrystallised from benzene as colourless crystals, m.p. 207–09°d, C₉H₈N₂O₃, soluble in benzene and chloroform; ν_{max} 3 420–3 260 (NH), 2 980–2 920, 1 760–1 745 (N–COOCH₃) and 1 590–1 550 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (100 MHz, CDCl₃), 3.7 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 7.2 (2H, s,